

Electrode kinetics and ternary complexes of [Mn^{II}-antibiotics-vitamin-B₂] vis-à-vis kinetics of electrode reaction

Santosh Narayan Chadar and Farid Khan*

Electrochemical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar-470 003,
Madhya Pradesh, India

E-mail : faridkhan58@yahoo.com ; farid.fk@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 11 September 2006, accepted 19 September 2006

Abstract : Polarographic technique was used to study the ternary complex formation of Mn^{II} with neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, penicillin-V and penicillin-G as primary ligands and vitamin-B₂ as a secondary ligand at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01 and μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄ at 298 K. The nature of current voltage curves was quasireversible. Mn^{II} formed 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes with these drugs as confirmed by Schaap and McMaster method. The sequence of stability constant of complexes was neomycin < chlortetracycline < oxytetracycline < tetracycline < penicillin-V < penicillin-G that can be explained on the basis of nature of ligands and steric hindrance between metals ligands. Kinetic parameters were also determined using Tamamushi and Tanaka method. The value of transfer coefficient (α) confirmed that the 'transition state' behaves between dropping mercury electrode and solution interface. A slight variation of potential affects not only the rate but rate constant greatly.

Keywords : Electrode kinetics, ternary complexes, vitamin-B₂, Mn^{II} complexes.

Vitamin-B₂ (riboflavin) is a water-soluble vitamin. Its metabolism is controlled by different hormones which regulate its conversion in FAD (flavin adenine dinucleotide) and FMN (flavin mononucleotide)^{1,2}. These two coenzymes catalyze many oxidation-reduction reactions and are essential for our production of energy.

On the other hand, antibiotics are natural compound produced mostly by plant microorganisms³ these antibiotics are used against several fungal and bacterial diseases in plants, animals and human beings⁴. Therefore, the study of complexes of antibiotics with riboflavin has great importance. In this paper, we report stability constant (log β) and kinetics parameters of complexes viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ), diffusion coefficient (D) and rate constant (k) of complexes using neomycin, chlortetracycline, oxytetracycline, tetracycline, penicillin-V, and penicillin-G as primary ligands and riboflavin as secondary ligands by polarographic technique for which no reference is available in the literature.

Results and discussion

Mn^{II} gave two electron quasireversible reduction wave at pH = 7.30 ± 0.01 and μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄ at 298 K⁵. The nature of current-voltage curves for complexes is also quasireversible. The concentration of Mn^{II}, NaClO₄,

and Triton X-100 (as suppressor) in the test solution were 0.5 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. Pure nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution for deaeration before recording the current-voltage curves.

The concentration of antibiotics varied from 0.5 mM to 30.0 mM at two fixed concentration of vitamin-B₂ i.e. 0.025 M and 0.050 M. The E_{1/2} values became more negative with the addition of vitamin-B₂ to the [Mn^{II}-antibiotics] system which showed ternary complex formation of 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2, and 1 : 2 : 1 complexes. Gellings⁶ method was used to determine the values of E_{1/2}^{reversible} form E_{1/2}^{quasireversible} by plotting (E - RT/nF log i_d - i/i) vs i for all the complexes. The data and plots of F_{ij} [X,Y] against [X] (where F_{ij} is a Schaap and McMaster⁷ function to evaluate the stability constant β_{ij}, X = neomycin, Y = vitamin-B₂ and i and j are their stoichiometric numbers respectively) for [Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin-B₂] system were given in Table 1 and Fig. 1 respectively. The Fig. 1 is used to determine the values of functions F₀₀, F₁₀, F₂₀ and F₃₀ and also to calculate the stability constant.

To know the values of β₁₁ and β₁₂, the study has been carried out at two constant concentration of secondary ligand [Y] = [vitamin-B₂] at 0.025 M and 0.050 M respectively. The values of stability constant of complexes

Table 1. Polarographic characteristics and F_{ij}[X, Y] values of [Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin-B₂] system^a

[Mn^{II}] = 0.050 M, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 ± 0.01, Temp. = 25 °C

[Neo] × 10 ³	[Vitamin-B ₂] = 0.025 M						[Vitamin-B ₂] = 0.050 M					
	log I _m /I _c	E _{1/2} ^r -V vs SCE	F ₀₀ [X, Y]	F ₁₀ [X, Y] × 10 ³	F ₂₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁴	F ₃₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁶	log I _m /I _c	E _{1/2} ^r -V vs SCE	F ₀₀ [X, Y]	F ₁₀ [X, Y] × 10 ³	F ₂₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁴	F ₃₀ [X, Y] × 10 ⁶
0.00	-	1.400	-	-	-	-	-	1.400	-	-	-	-
0.50	0.0074	1.416	3.63	567.31	102.12	10.00	0.0074	1.425	6.23	1826.60	197.67	10.00
1.00	0.0149	1.419	4.69	1080.45	102.62	10.00	0.0149	1.427	7.14	2819.98	198.17	10.01
2.00	0.0149	1.426	8.39	1598.59	103.12	10.01	0.0149	1.435	9.05	4821.71	199.17	10.00
3.00	0.0226	1.433	14.26	2649.85	104.12	10.00	0.0149	1.441	15.87	6843.63	200.18	10.02
4.00	0.0304	1.438	22.34	3721.30	105.13	10.02	0.0226	1.447	26.76	8885.68	201.18	10.03
5.00	0.0304	1.443	32.71	4812.86	106.13	10.03	0.0226	1.452	41.77	10947.19	202.17	10.01
6.00	0.0384	1.447	45.42	5923.90	107.13	10.01	0.0304	1.456	60.97	13028.68	203.17	10.00
8.00	0.0384	1.454	78.13	7054.92	108.13	10.04	0.0384	1.462	84.40	17254.72	205.20	10.04
10.00	0.0465	1.460	120.92	9380.02	110.15	10.03	0.0384	1.468	144.27	21558.65	207.20	10.03
20.00	0.0465	1.478	503.27	11782.99	112.15	10.04	0.0465	1.485	221.82	44289.06	217.25	10.04
30.00	0.0465	1.489	1210.06	40232.35	132.21	10.03	0.0465	1.496	2076.75	69017.48	227.26	10.03

log A = 0.490, log B = 2.75, log C = 6.009, log D = 7.00

log A = 0.794, log B = 2.923, log C = 8.295, log D = 7.00

^aThe data for other systems can be obtained on request.

were given in Table 3.

To compare the stability of binary and ternary complexes. The values of mixing constant log k was calculated by the following equation⁷

$$\log k_m = \log \beta_{11} - 1/2 [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

Fig. 1. Plot of F_{ij}[X, Y] vs [X] for [Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin-B₂] system.

The values of log k_m were -0.625, -0.31, 2.69, -5.025, -0.99, and -0.79 for [Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin-B₂], [Mn^{II}-chlortetracycline-vitamin-B₂], [Mn^{II}-tetracycline-vitamin-B₂], and [Mn^{II}-penicillin-G-vitamin-B₂], respectively. The positive value of log k_m showed that the ternary complex is more stable than their binary complexes while the negative values of log k_m showed that binary complexes are more stable than their ternary complexes. The complexes of compositions 1 : 1 : 1, 1 : 1 : 2 and 1 : 2 : 1, in case of [Mn^{II}-oxytetracycline-vitamin-B₂] and [Mn^{II}-penicilline-V-vitamin-B₂] are not formed therefore; the values of log k_m were not calculated. It is clear from the values of stability constants of complexes that neomycin formed the complexes of lowest stability. In case of tetracycline; all the tetracycline have the same structures except in the difference in R₁ and R₂ position. The lesser stability constant of chlortetracycline complex than that of oxytetracycline complex is due to the presence of more electrons withdrawing Cl at R₁ in the former in place of H in the latter. In case of tetracycline, H is present both at R₁ and R₂ hence; there are least electronic disturbances in tetracycline in comparison to other tetracycline complexes⁸. This order of stability supported the order of their pK values of the ligands⁹. In case of both penicillin-V and penicillin-G, it is the ring nitrogen and O of the carboxylic group which take part in complexation with Mn^{II}. The greater stability of penicillin-G complexes than that of penicillin-V complexes is also supported by the order of

Table 2. Kinetics parameters of $[Mn^{II}$ -neomycin-vitamin- B_2] system^a[Mn^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01, Temp. = 25°C

[Neo] $\times 10^3$	[Vitamin- B_2] = 0.025 M						[Vitamin- B_2] = 0.050 M					
	$(E_{1/2})^{gr}$ -V vs SCE	Slop (mV)	α	λ (s ^{-1/2})	$D_{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)	$(E_{1/2})^{gr}$ -V vs SCE	Slop (mV)	α	λ (s ^{-1/2})	$D_{1/2} \times 10^3$ (cm ² s ⁻¹)	$k \times 10^3$ (cm s ⁻¹)
0.00	1.410	37.0	0.42	2.02	3.82	7.73	1.410	37.0	0.42	2.02	3.82	7.73
0.50	1.418	37.5	0.44	1.02	3.98	4.09	1.426	40.0	0.49	1.63	3.98	6.52
1.00	1.420	35.0	0.48	1.46	3.91	5.71	1.430	35.0	0.45	1.16	3.91	4.53
2.00	1.428	35.0	0.48	1.63	3.91	6.40	1.438	35.0	0.51	1.30	3.91	5.09
3.00	1.436	35.0	0.49	1.16	3.84	4.45	1.445	40.0	0.48	1.16	3.91	4.53
4.00	1.440	35.0	0.49	1.16	3.77	4.37	1.450	35.0	0.47	1.30	3.84	5.00
5.00	1.445	40.0	0.47	1.63	3.70	5.41	1.455	37.5	0.46	1.30	3.84	5.00
6.00	1.450	35.0	0.47	1.46	3.77	6.18	1.460	40.0	0.48	1.46	3.77	5.11
8.00	1.456	45.0	0.50	1.16	3.70	4.30	1.464	45.0	0.46	1.16	3.70	4.30
10.00	1.465	40.0	0.52	1.30	3.63	4.73	1.470	40.0	0.47	1.02	3.70	3.81
20.00	1.480	37.5	0.49	1.02	3.63	3.73	1.488	40.0	0.55	1.02	3.63	3.75
30.00	1.492	35.5	0.49	1.02	3.63	3.73	1.500	45.0	0.51	1.16	3.63	4.22

^aThe data for other systems can be obtained on request.Table 3. Stability constants of $[Mn^{II}$ -antibiotics-vitamin- B_2] system[Mn^{II}] = 0.5 mM, μ = 1.0 M NaClO₄, pH = 7.30 \pm 0.01, Temp. = 25 °C

Primary ligand	log β_{01}	log β_{02}	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
Neomycin	-	-	2.92	4.85	7.00	3.26	5.08	7.58
Chlortetracycline	-	-	3.31	5.02	7.78	3.66	5.35	8.00
Oxytetracycline	-	-	4.00	-	8.13	4.45	6.12	8.56
Tetracycline	-	-	4.12	7.13	8.26	-	7.32	8.56
Penicillin-V	-	-	4.31	7.76	8.60	4.35	7.83	8.95
Penicillin-G	-	-	4.40	8.00	9.00	4.67	8.20	9.13
Vitamin- B_2	1.80	2.92	-	-	-	-	-	-

the pK values¹⁰.

In case of vitamin- B_2 , it is the N of pyrimidine ring¹¹, which can take part in bond formation with Mn^{II} .

It is clear from the values of stability constant of the complexes that vitamin- B_2 and antibiotics used either singly or simultaneously might be effective to reduce the toxicity¹² of Mn^{II} *in vivo*.

The kinetic parameters viz. transfer coefficient (α), degree of irreversibility (λ) and rate constant (k) were determined by Tamamushi and Tanaka methods^{13,14} by plotting ($E'_{1/2} - E$) against log ($Z - 1$) (Figs. 2(a) and 2(b), where the terms have the usual significance)^{13,14}. The values of kinetic parameters were given in Table 2. It is obvious from the value of α that the values varied from [Mn^{II}-neomycin-vitamin- B_2] 0.42 to 0.52 (about 0.50), and value of α for other systems were also about 0.50 confirmed that 'transition state' lies midway between drop-

ping mercury electrode and solution interface. The value of rate constant (k) showed that the electrode process were quasireversible. The values of diffusion coefficient as determined by Ilkovic equation¹⁵ were as expected.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Mn^{II} , the antibiotics and vitamin- B_2 were taken in the ratios of 1 : 40 : 40 and current voltage curves were obtained in different pH values. It has been observed that the maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was obtained within the pH range 7.10–8.50, but pH 7.30 was selected for studying the complexes in human blood pH. A Systronic μ pH meter 361 was used to measure the pH of the analyte at 7.30 \pm 0.01 adjusted by using dilute solutions of HClO₄ or NaOH as required. Potassium dihydrogen phosphate-sodium hydroxide buffer was added to stabilize the pH of the analyte.

Fig. 2(a). $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}\text{-neomycin-vitamin-B}_2]$ system, $[\text{vitamin-B}_2] = 0.025 \text{ mM}$.

Plot of $(E_{1/2}^r - E)$ versus $\log(Z-1)$, Y-axis = $\log(Z-1)$, X-axis = $(E_{1/2}^r - E)$.

Fig. 2(b). $[Mn^{II}$ -neomycin-vitamin- $B_2]$ system, $[vitamin-B_2] = 0.050$ mM.

Plot of $(E_{1/2} - E)$ versus $\log(Z - 1)$, Y-axis = $\log(Z - 1)$, X-axis = $(E_{1/2} - E)$.

The current voltage curves were obtained on a manual polarograph using polyflex galvanometer (PL-50). The polarographic cell was of Latinin and Lingane type in which polarographic capillary of 5.0 cm in length with 0.04 mm in diameter was used. The $m^{2/3} t^{1/6}$ value was $2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.02 cm effective height of mercury. As the resistance of the cell was less than 300Ω , IR correction was not made.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Head, Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour University, Sagar, for providing the laboratory facilities.

References

1. L. S. Goodman and Gilman, "The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics", McMillan Publisher Co., New York, 1980, 1555.
2. B. M. Barker and D. A. Bender, "Vitamins in Medicines", William Heinemann Medical Books Ltd., London, 1995, 386.
3. T. Korzybski, Z. Kowszyk-Gindifer and W. Kuryloicz, "Antibiotics Origin, Nature and Properties", Pwn Polish Scientific Publishers, Warszawa, 1967, 1.
4. A. K. Kesharwani and F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2002, **18**, 413.
5. F. Khan and L. Tantuvay, *J. Pharm. Biomed. Anal. (Netherland)*, 2002, **27**, 933.
6. P. J. Gellings, *Z. Electrochem Ber Bunsenges Phys. Chem.*, 1962, **66**, 481; 1963, **67**, 167.
7. W. B. Schaap and D. L. McMaster, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.
8. R. S. Mulliken, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1935, **3**, 513.
9. J. M. Desiqueria, S. Carvalho, E. B. Paniago, L. Tosi and H. Beraldo, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1994, **83**, 291.
10. B. P. Chakraworti, A. Tiwari and H. N. Sharma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 200.
11. F. Khan, *Bull. Electrochem.*, 2003, **19**, 283.
12. M. D. Walker and D. R. Williams, *J. Chem. Soc. (Dalton)*, 1974, 1186.
13. R. Tamamushi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neue Folge*, 1963, **39**, 117.
14. R. Tamamushi, K. Ishibashi and N. Tanaka, *Z. Phys. Chem., Neue Folge*, 1962, **35**, 211.
15. D. Ilkovic, *Collec. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1936, **8**, 13.